

Determination of Copper and Cadmium Present together in the Binary Mixtures

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This paper reports the results of the determination of copper and cadmium present together in the binary mixtures in low concentrations biamprometrically using two stationary platinum electrodes at constant applied potential of 0.9 volts. The pH at which the determination was carried out was 3.5 for copper and 4.5 for cadmium.

A study of the available literature¹ shows that scarcely attempt has so far been made for the quantitative determination of copper and cadmium present in a mixture by electrometric titrations. Cihalik and others² estimated copper and cadmium in a binary mixture using ethanolic mercaptobenzo-thiazol as a titrant.

The present studies report on the application of biamprometry for a rapid and direct determination of copper and cadmium present in their binary mixtures at low concentration using EDTA as a titrant.

Experimental

Copper and cadmium salts used were of B.D.H. or Merck's extrapure quality. The respective sulphates of copper and cadmium were dissolved separately in conductivity water and their contents estimated using standard methods³. Standard EDTA solution (.05M) was prepared and standardized using standard methods³. Salts solutions were obtained after appropriate dilution of the stock solution. Conductivity water was used for dilution and preparation of solutions.

The apparatus and the experimental arrangements used were same as described in the earlier papers⁴. 20 ml of the test solution containing copper and cadmium was placed in the titration cell with proper amount of monochloroacetate buffer, pH 3.5 at an applied potential of 0.9 volts. A stream of nitrogen passed for 5 minutes. EDTA solution was added from a 2.0 ml semimicroburette and the solution was stirred using magnetic stirrer. With the addition of EDTA solution cupric ions chelate the current remains constant till the equivalence point when EDTA completely complexes the cupric ions and thereafter the current begins to increase. Cadmium does not interfere with copper estimation at this pH. When the estimation of copper is complete the pH of the mixture is altered using acetate buffer and adjusted to 4.6. Next the titration is continued at the same applied potential. Cadmium starts getting chelated with the further addition of EDTA and

the current remains steady and increase with the excess of titrant. The graphs obtained by these titrations contain two intersections on the residual current line. The first end point is corresponding to completion of copper determination and the second is corresponding to the sum of copper and cadmium estimation; the amount of latter is computed by the difference. The curve has the shape as shown in Fig. (1). Experiments were repeated

Fig. 1.

Amount observed, mg
Copper 0.1913
Cadmium 0.2810

several times for concordance and the results of such determination are given in Table 1.

TABLE-1

DETERMINATION OF COPPER AND CADMIUM PRESENT TOGETHER IN THE BINARY MIXTURES					
Amount of cadmium, mg			Amount of copper, mg		
Taken	Found	Difference	Taken	Found	Difference
0.2810	0.2810	±0.0000	0.1906	0.1913	+0.0007
0.2248	0.2259	+0.0011	0.1271	0.1271	±0.0000
0.1967	0.1978	+0.0006	0.1271	0.1277	+0.0006
0.1686	0.1681	-0.0005	0.1191	0.1202	+0.0001
0.1124	0.1115	-0.0009	0.0953	0.0962	+0.0009

Results and Discussion

The method described is based on electro-oxidation of free EDTA on a platinum anode in the pH range 3.5 to 4.5. On addition of EDTA solution metal chelates are formed and no electro-oxidation of EDTA occurs. If a potential of the order of 0.9 volts is applied to two platinum electrodes the residual current is registered up to the equivalence point but the current rises abruptly due to the oxidation of EDTA after the equivalence point. The method is sensitive even at low concentrations and the electrode system is both compact and simple; and would be very useful for the analysis of alloys and minerals. Results are within the limits of experimental errors.

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